

Women Entrepreneurship

R.Buvaneshwari, B.Com., M.Com.,
II – M.Com, Annai Women’s College, Karur

V.Abinaya, B.Com., M.Com.,
II – M.Com, Annai Women’s College, Karur

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 2

Month: February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Buvaneshwari, R., and
V. Abinaya. “Women
Entrepreneurship.”
*Shanlax International
Journal of Commerce*,
vol. 7, no. S2, 2019,
pp. 61–63.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.2563777](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2563777)

Abstract

Women Entrepreneurship is considered as an important tool in eradicating poverty and unemployment. Now a day’s Women empowerment has become a buzzword. Empowerment of women may not be feasible just by creating employment opportunity for them. The need of the hour is to inspire them to set up their own enterprises. Traditionally, women have been on stage, by playing a crucial role in the management of the family as well as in the society. But their job has not been duly recognized. She is active in family, farms, shop, and factory and even in politics. Women entrepreneurs are gaining momentum all over the world, but at the same time they are facing a number of challenges. These challenges can be faced with making them and their family aware of the opportunities available to them. Hence the support of family members is essential for leveraging their creative talent. The paper focuses on opportunities for growth and challenges faced by women entrepreneurs of today. The paper is based on women Roti makers working in Gulbarga city of Karnataka state in India.

Introduction

“A women entrepreneur is a confident, innovative and creative women capable of achieving self-economic independence individually or in collaboration, generates employment opportunities for others through initiating, establishing and running the enterprise by keeping pace with her personal, family and social life.”

Women entrepreneur may be defined as a women or group of women who initiate, organize, and run a business enterprise. In terms of Schumpeterian concept of innovative entrepreneurs, women who innovate, imitate or adopt a business activity are called “women entrepreneurs”. Kamal Singh who is a woman entrepreneur from Rajasthan, has defined woman entrepreneur as “a confident, innovative and creative woman capable of achieving self-economic independence individually or in collaboration, generates employment opportunity for others through initiating, establishing and running the enterprise by keeping pace with her personal, family and social life.” The Government of India has defined women entrepreneurs based on women participation in equity and employment of a business enterprise. Accordingly, the Government of India (GOI 2006) has defined women entrepreneur as “an enterprise owned and controlled by a women having a minimum financial interest of 51 per cent of the capital and giving at least 51 per cent of the employment generate in the enterprise to women.”

Functions of Women Entrepreneurship

- Exploration of the prospects of starting a new business enterprise.
- Undertaking of risks and the handling of economic uncertainties involved in business.
- Introduction of innovation or imitation of innovations.
- Coordination, administration and control.
- Supervision and leadership.

Problems of Women Entrepreneurships

- **PROBLEMS OF FINANCE:** Finance is regarded as “life-blood” for any enterprise, be it big or small.
- **SCARCITY OF RAW MATERIAL:** Most of the women enterprises are plagued by the scarcity of raw material and necessary inputs.
- **STIFF COMPETITION:** Women entrepreneurs do not have organization set-up to pumps in a lot of money for canvassing and advertisement.
- **LIMITED MOBILITY:** Women mobility in India is highly limited due to various reasons. A single women asking for room is still looked upon suspicion.
- **FAMILY TIES:** Support and approval of husbands seem necessary condition for women’s entry into business.
- **MALE DOMINATED SOCIETY:** Women suffer from male reservation about a women’s role, ability and capacity and are treated accordingly.
- **LOW RISK-BEARING ABILITY:** Women in India Idea a protected life. They are less educated and economically not self-dependent.

Concept of Women Entrepreneurship

Women entrepreneurs are those women who conceive the idea of a business enterprise initiate it organize and combine the factors of production, operate the enterprise, undertake risks and manage the economic uncertainty involved in running a business enterprise.

A women or a group of people who initiate, organize and run a business enterprise is defined as “women entrepreneur. The government of India has defined women entrepreneur as “an enterprise owned and controlled by a women having a minimum financial interest of 51% of the capital and fixing atleast 51% of the employment generated in the enterprises to women”.

Leadership Qualities

Some of the outstanding qualities of women entrepreneurs are as follows:

- | | |
|----------------------|----------------------------|
| 1. Accept Challenges | 9. Adventurous |
| 2. Driver | 10. Conscious |
| 3. Hard work | 11. Educated |
| 4. Motivations | 12. Determination to excel |
| 5. Skill full | 13. Experienced |
| 6. Industrious | 14. Intelligent |
| 7. Studious | 15. Perseverance |
| 8. Patience | 16. Unquenchable optimism |

Fostering Factors

Motivational Needs

- Economic necessity
- Independences

- Education and qualification
- Family occupation
- Success stories of friends of friends & relatives

Facilitating Needs

- Adequate financial facilities
- Experienced and skilled people at work
- Development training programs
- Cooperation of family
- Indian scenario
- In India, women comprise about 30% of corporate senior management positions, which is notably higher than the global average (24%). But in the overall workforce, India is one of the worst countries in the world-113th out of 135-when it comes of entrepreneurs in the country.
- It is believed that women entrepreneurs have an edge over male entrepreneurs. Edges matter to investors. And the numbers back this up outside India.
- A Dow Jones study called women at the Wheel: Do Female Executives Drive Startup Success? Offers some interesting conclusions:
- The overall median proportion of female executives in successful companies is 7.1%, compared to 3.1% at unsuccessful companies.
- A company's odds of success increase with female executive at the VP and directors levels.
- Statistically significant evidence shows that there is dependence between a company having female executive and its success.

Conclusion

Entrepreneurship among women, no doubt improves the nation in general and of the family in particular. Women today are more willing to take up activities that once considered the preserve of men, and have proved that are second to no one with respect to contribution to the growth of the economy. Women entrepreneurship must be molded properly with entrepreneurial traits and skill to meet the changes in trends, challenges global markets and also be competent enough to sustain and strive for excellence in the entrepreneurial arena.

References

- Bose upEster. "Women's Role in Economic Development". St Martin's, New York. 1970
- Gupta, CB., & Khanka, SS. "Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management". *Sultan Chand & Sons*, Delhi. 1996.
- Khanka, SS., & Chand, S. "Company Ltd, New Delhi". *Entrepreneurial Development*. pp. 52-63, 2008.
- Rajendran, N. "Problem and Prospects of Women Entrepreneurs" 2003.